

QUIET
CORNERS

ARE THERE VOICES WE
HAVEN'T HEARD?

DOMINATING VOICE

IT SEEMS LIKE SOME VOICES AREN'T GETTING
MUCH SPACE: CAN WE LISTEN TO OTHER PERSPECTIVES?

FRAGMENTED FOCUS

THE CONVERSATION FEELS SCATTERED OR HARD TO FOLLOW. WHAT ARE THE ISSUES WE NEED TO FOCUS ON?

CIRCLING THE ISSUES

WHAT MIGHT HELP US TAKE THE
NEXT STEP TOGETHER?

BENEATH THE SURFACE

WHAT IS IMPORTANT FOR US AND FOR OTHERS? OFFER AND ASK ABOUT CONCERNS AND REASONS BEHIND POSITIONS

MEETING THE OTHER

CAN WE REFORMULATE WHAT WE
LEARNT FROM THE OTHERS?

SHIFTING THE LENS

COULD WE BE LOOKING AT THE SAME THINGS
IN DIFFERENT WAYS?

THE FIRE BENEATH

EVERYBODY'S EMOTIONS AND SENTIMENTS ARE IMPORTANT.
DO WE WANT TO SHARE MORE IN THE DIALOGUE?

FROM SELF TO SYSTEM

DISAGREEMENT IS NOT A FAILURE! ACKNOWLEDGE THAT
DISAGREEMENT IS NORMAL IN DIALOGUE

EMPTY
CHAIR

ARE THERE ANY VOICES OR GROUPS
MISSING FROM THIS CONVERSATION?